

ADSORBENT FOR REMOVING ACIDIC IMPURITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881020>

Abstract. This paper presents the results of a study on the development of modified adsorbents based on local raw materials - bentonite from the Navbakhor deposit, Navoi region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Trimethylammonium (TMA) and triethylammonium (TEA) were used as bentonite activators, and the absorption capacity of adsorbents with respect to acidic components (H_2S and CO_2) and moisture, their regenerability, as well as the kinetic characteristics of the reaction with acid gases were studied. Based on the experimental results, it was found that the sorption capacity is 0.20-0.21 mol/l for H_2S and 20.6-21.0 mol/l for CO_2 , while in relation to currently widely used imported foreign countries, the proposed modified adsorbents absorb 40% more hydrogen sulfide and 60% CO_2 .

Keywords: sorbent, modification, sorption capacity, bentonite, acidic impurities, absorption capacity.

Currently, one of the most important tasks of modern colloid chemist is to obtain materials with predetermined properties. In this regard, the problem of regulating surface properties for such materials as adsorbents, carriers, catalysts, the effective participation of which in various technological processes is due precisely to surface properties, such as the nature of active centers, porosity, etc., becomes of great importance [1-4].

The paper presents the results of a study of the absorption capacity of adsorbents based on Navbakhor bentonite modified by TMA and TEA. The absorption capacity of adsorbents with respect to acidic components (H_2S and CO_2) and moisture, their regenerability, as well as the kinetic characteristics of the reaction with acid gases were determined using a model gas consisting of 1.98% volume hydrogen sulfide and 98.02% volume hydrogen sulfide nitrogen and real hydrocarbon gases supplied to sulfur production plants at the Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex (SHGCC).

The absorption capacity with respect to hydrogen sulfide, determined using a model gas, is presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Fig.1. Effect of activator concentration on hydrogen sulfide absorption.

The absorption capacity of the modified TMA adsorbent (up to 10-15% wt.) with a concentration of 5-10% has a high sorption capacity and is 0.20-0.21 mol/l for H₂S and 20.6-21.0 for CO₂.

While in relation to those currently widely used, those imported from foreign countries absorb 40% more hydrogen sulfide and 60% CO₂.

With an increase in the concentration of TMA and TEA in the composition of bentonite from Navbakhor deposit, the absorption capacity decreases, which is due to the polarity of the medium. Tests carried out on a model gas confirm the assumptions about the increased absorption capacity of adsorbents obtained on the basis of Navbakhor bentonite and modified with TMA and TEA solutions in relation to hydrogen sulfide and carbon monoxide compared to the used imported adsorbents.

The results of studying the kinetic patterns of the adsorption capacity of Navbakhor bentonite modified with TMA and TEA are given in Table 1 and 2.

Fig.2. Dependence of the degree of CO₂ absorption of acid gases on the concentration of activators

Table 1

Kinetic characteristics of separate adsorption and desorption of acid gases.

Procedure	Bentonite with TMA		Bentonite with TEA	
	Energy activation kJ/mol	Pre-expo-insignificant factor	Energy activation kJ/mol	Pre-expo-insignificant factor
Adsorption hydrogen sulfide	18,0	13,5	20,0	14,2
Desorption hydrogen sulfide	20,5	35,5	21,0	36,8
Adsorption carbon dioxide gas	15,0	11,9	17,0	16,4

Desorption carbon dioxide gas	16,5	1,9	18,5	3,1
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Table 2

Kinetic characteristics of joint adsorption and desorption of acid gases

Procedure	Bentonite with TMA		Bentonite with TEA	
	Energy activation kJ/mol	Pre-expo- insignificant factor	Energy activation kJ/mol	Pre-expo- insignificant factor
Adsorption hydrogen sulfide	21,0	54,5	23,0	41,2
Desorption hydrogen sulfide	22,5	23,5	25,5	38,5
Adsorption carbon dioxide gas	17,0	14,3	20,0	18,5
Desorption carbon dioxide gas	18,5	4,9	21,0	8,5

Thus, for the first time, the adsorption abilities of adsorbents obtained on the basis of Navbakhor bentonite and modified with solutions of TMA and TEA were studied in comparison with the adsorbents currently used at ShGCC.

It has been established that an increase in the concentration of trimethylammonium (TMA) and triethylammonium (TEA) in bentonites leads to an increase in the sorption capacity of acid gases. In this case, the optimal concentration of TMA and TEA solutions is 10-15%. It was revealed that modified adsorbents, in addition to high adsorption capacity, have thermal stability.

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